

³²P Tracer Investigation on Phosphorus Utilization by Soybean in Vertisol

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A pot culture experiment was carried out with four levels of phosphorus using ³²P tagged superphosphate (viz. 0, 40, 80 and 120 kg P₂O₅/ha) and three varieties of soybean namely Punjab-1, JS-2 and Gaurav to study the uptake and utilization of applied fertilizer phosphorus in vertisol of Jabalpur. Dry matter yield, total P uptake, and percent P derived from fertilizer increased significantly with increasing levels of phosphorus. But percent utilization of added P showed a reverse trend, at all the stages of crop growth. Grain and straw yield at harvest increased significantly with increasing P levels in all the three varieties.

It is well known that when phosphate fertilizers are added to vertisol, which are fine to fine textured soils with more than 35% clay having montmorillonite as predominant clay mineral, the phosphorus reacts with soil and gets fixed and only a small fraction of it remains in the available form. The present study was undertaken to investigate the comparative and combined effect of phosphorus on utilization by different varieties of soybean at various stages of growth in a vertisol.

Experimental

The experiment was conducted in the pot house of the department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, J. N. Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur with 3 varieties of soybean and 4 levels of phosphorus in *kharif*, 1980. Soil samples were collected from experimental area and filled in 10 kg capacity pots. The soil contained 0.6% organic carbon and 240, 10 and 268 kg/ha available N, P and K₂O, respectively. The pH of the soil was 7.2. A basal application of 20 kg N and 40 kg K₂O was applied at the time of sowing. Urea, single superphosphate and muriate of potash were used as the source of N, P and K respectively.

Soybean varieties, Punjab-1, JS-2 and Gaurav were chosen as the test crop. Four levels of phosphorus viz. 0 (control), 40, 80 and 120 kg P₂O₅/ha were used as tagged superphosphate having specific activity of 0.4 mCi/g P₂O₅ which was procured from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay. The radio-active phosphorus in plant materials was determined by the method of Mackenzie and Dean¹. Counting for radio-active P was done by placing the sample under identical geometric conditions in Geiger Muller counter. The total P uptake was determined by the method of Koenig and Johnson².

Results and Discussion

It is evident from Table 1 that the total phosphorus uptake increased significantly with increasing level of phosphorus at all stages of growth in all the varieties. This might be due to the higher availability of P with increasing P levels. Similar findings were also reported by Ham and Caldwell³ and Gate and Muller⁴.

The data revealed (Table 2) that the percent phosphorus derived from fertilizer increased

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF PHOSPHORUS LEVELS ON TOTAL P UPTAKE (mg/pot) BY SOYBEAN AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF GROWTH

P levels kg P ₂ O ₅ / ha.	30 DAY STAGE				FLOWERING STAGE				HARVESTING STAGE							
	Pun- jab-1	JS-2	Gau- rav	Mean	Pun- jab-1	JS-2	Gau- rav	Mean	GRAIN				STRAW			
									Pun- jab-1	JS-2	Gau- rav	Mean	Pun- jab-1	JS-2	Gau- rav	Mean
P ₀	6.19	7.75	6.36	6.93	16.58	16.50	18.80	17.29	48.47	52.71	47.91	49.69	6.90	5.86	5.36	6.04
P ₄₀	10.34	9.73	9.22	9.76	22.84	25.46	26.89	24.96	68.32	70.05	66.31	68.22	9.41	8.08	8.55	8.68
P ₈₀	11.97	12.12	10.97	11.68	34.01	34.73	31.71	33.48	85.46	90.09	85.90	89.15	12.07	11.75	11.06	11.64
P ₁₂₀	12.69	13.49	12.17	12.78	36.43	40.60	39.34	38.79	103.80	103.53	96.55	101.29	13.99	23.26	13.27	13.50
Mean	10.29	10.77	9.80		27.46	29.32	29.11		76.61	79.10	74.16		10.59	9.73	9.56	
Effect	P		V		P		V		P		V		P		V	
S.Em ±	0.38		0.33		0.67		0.58		1.97		1.70		0.44		0.38	
C.D. at 5%	1.13		NS		1.94		1.68		5.73		NS		1.29		NS	

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PHOSPHORUS LEVELS ON PHOSPHORUS DERIVED FROM FERTILIZER (%) BY SOYBEAN AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF GROWTH

P levels kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha.	30 DAY STAGE				FLOWERING STAGE				HARVESTING STAGE								
	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	GRAIN				STRAW				
									Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	
P ₀	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
P ₄₀	22.86	21.02	20.47	21.45	40.23	40.43	39.79	40.15	22.91	21.74	21.81	23.82	28.32	33.12	30.83	30.75	
P ₈₀	26.16	32.42	27.36	28.65	46.82	47.61	47.17	47.20	32.66	30.78	32.93	32.12	33.10	38.41	37.19	36.23	
P ₁₂₀	30.65	35.84	43.48	32.99	52.31	51.38	49.96	51.21	33.14	36.74	33.41	36.10	39.05	38.35	38.77	39.05	
Mean	26.55	29.76	26.77		46.65	46.47	45.64		31.24	29.75	31.05		33.49	36.96	35.59		
Effect	P				P				P				P				
S.E.m ±	0.86				0.57				0.80				0.93				
C.D. at 5%	2.55				1.72				2.40				2.78				

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF PHOSPHORUS LEVELS ON P UTILIZATION (%) BY SOYBEAN AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF GROWTH

P levels kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha.	30 DAY STAGE				FLOWERING STAGE				HARVESTING STAGE							
	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	GRAIN				STRAW			
									Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean
P ₀	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
P ₄₀	2.65	2.30	2.12	2.35	10.37	11.59	11.86	11.28	17.62	17.08	19.81	18.17	2.99	3.02	2.96	2.99
P ₈₀	1.75	2.20	1.62	1.85	8.91	9.30	8.41	8.87	15.67	15.62	15.84	15.71	2.24	2.53	2.29	2.35
P ₁₂₀	1.48	1.81	1.52	1.60	7.14	7.82	7.31	7.42	14.97	14.25	12.07	13.76	2.04	1.96	1.91	1.97
Mean	1.96	2.10	1.75		8.80	9.57	9.20		16.09	15.65	15.91		2.42	2.50	2.39	
Effect	P				P				P				P			
S.E.m ±	0.071				0.262				0.430				0.129			
C.D. at 5%	0.21				0.77				1.27				0.38			

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF PHOSPHORUS LEVELS ON SOIL P UPTAKE (mg/pot) BY SOYBEAN AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF GROWTH

P levels kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha.	30 DAY STAGE				FLOWERING STAGE				HARVESTING STAGE							
	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	GRAIN				STRAW			
									Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean
P ₀	6.19	7.75	5.86	6.60	16.58	16.50	18.80	17.29	48.47	52.71	41.91	47.69	6.90	5.88	5.36	6.04
P ₄₀	7.08	6.69	7.33	7.36	13.63	15.15	16.01	14.93	52.66	54.88	48.70	52.08	6.75	5.39	5.92	6.02
P ₈₀	8.84	8.18	8.05	8.35	18.17	18.19	16.74	17.70	57.59	62.65	57.73	59.32	8.09	7.24	6.98	7.43
P ₁₂₀	9.00	8.64	8.65	8.76	17.39	19.74	19.83	18.98	64.28	65.18	64.35	64.60	8.53	8.10	8.16	8.26
Mean	7.77	8.06	7.47		16.44	17.39	17.84		55.75	58.85	53.17		7.56	6.65	4.58	
Effect	P				P				P				P			
S.E.m ±	0.31				0.47				1.83				0.34			
C.D. at 5%	NS				1.37				NS				NS			

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF PHOSPHORUS LEVELS ON DRY MATTER PRODUCTION OF SOYBEAN AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF GROWTH (g/pot)

P levels kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha.	30 DAY STAGE				FLOWERING STAGE				HARVESTING STAGE							
	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	GRAIN				STRAW			
									Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean	Pun-jab-1	JS-2	Gau-rav	Mean
P ₀	3.53	4.33	3.73	3.86	8.06	7.52	8.37	7.98	8.47	9.19	8.97	8.37	11.22	10.17	9.65	10.41
P ₄₀	5.21	4.53	4.10	4.61	9.76	10.27	11.18	10.40	10.63	10.32	10.02	10.32	12.94	11.96	12.09	12.33
P ₈₀	5.67	5.35	4.56	5.19	11.66	12.06	11.80	11.84	11.54	11.94	11.57	11.68	14.57	14.55	13.78	14.30
P ₁₂₀	5.73	5.47	5.11	5.43	11.55	12.65	12.34	12.18	12.54	12.39	12.34	12.42	15.41	14.93	14.76	15.03
Mean	5.03	4.92	4.37		10.25	10.62	10.92		10.79	10.96	10.72		13.53	12.90	12.62	
Effect	P				P				P				P			
S.E.m ±	0.14				0.26				0.24				0.22			
C.D. at 5%	0.41				0.75				0.71				0.65			

significantly with increasing level of phosphorus which might be due to the fact that the more the phosphatic fertilizers added to soil, the more the crop removal. On the other hand the P fixation capacity of soil being limited, an additional amount of P fertilizer added increased the pool of available phosphorus from which P was proportionately absorbed by the plants.

The percent utilization of phosphorus (Table 3) decreased significantly with increasing level of phosphorus at all the stages of growth in all varieties, which means that the utilization of added P was not in proportion to applied P level. On the other hand with lower dose the available amount of P was less than the need of the crop for its growth, as a result of which the efficiency of utilization of applied fertilizer P is high at low dose and low at higher dose. Similar results were also reported by Sinha *et al*⁶, Negi *et al*⁶, and Sinha *et al*⁷.

The data presented in Table 4 revealed that as the dose of phosphorus increased, the uptake of P from soil source also increased at all the growth stages. This might be due to the proportionately higher uptake of phosphorus with increased dry matter yield of crop as well as better root system development caused by phosphorus application which enabled the plant to exploit the P from soil to a greater extent. Similar findings were also reported by Sinha *et al*⁷.

From the results presented in Table 5 it is observed that the dry matter yield of soybean

increased at all the stages of growth with increasing level of P. This increased yield was due to the response of P over control indicating that the soil was not in a position to supply enough P as required by the crop and as soon as the phosphorus deficiency was made up, increased yield was obtained. Similar results were also reported by Mahajan and Bisen¹.

In conclusion we can say that application of increasing doses of phosphate fertilizer brings about increased uptake of P by the plant, increased dry matter yield and increased uptake of P from soil source. The phosphorus derived from fertilizer also increases but percent utilization of applied P decreases indicating thereby that the efficiency of P utilization is more at lower level of fertilization than at higher doses.

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